

TAILORING OF THE PRACTICAL ADHESION BETWEEN GALVANIZED STEEL AND POLYETHYLENE

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SUMMARY : The practical adhesion of maleic anhydride grafted polyethylene to galvanised steel was studied using 3-point flexure tests, before and after aging in water. Before bonding, the electro-galvanised steel was treated with different coatings based on γ -aminopropyltriethoxysilane (γ -APS). The influence of the coating thickness and of the pH of the coating on the practical adhesion were investigated. FTIR spectroscopy and microscopy allowed to gain understanding of the interphase formation between the metal substrate and the silane. It was found that at the natural pH of the γ -APS, the dissolution of Zn ions in the coating with subsequent formation of crystals is responsible for the better durability of the bonds than for coatings applied at neutral pH for which the partial dissolution was not observed. In a second part, hybrid coatings based on γ -APS blended with hyperbranched polymers were studied. Although the toughening effect of the hybrid coatings was shown in former studies, it was not possible in this study to show a positive effect of these coatings on practical adhesion.

KEYWORDS: galvanised steel, polyolefines, functionalised organo-silane, HBP, adhesion, ageing.

INTRODUCTION

Bonding and joining between polyolefins and steel are found in applications as diverse as steel reinforced polymers and in the automotive industry where steel and thermoplastics are commonly used. As polyolefins are highly unreactive, because of their low polarity, and present poor adhesion to polar (hydrophilic) substrates, it is necessary to optimise the interface to promote adhesion. This can be achieved by chemical modification of the bulk polymer matrix, by physico-chemical modification of one or both constituent's surfaces, and/or by the use of coupling agents, that are chemically reactive with both polymeric matrix and metal substrate. Moreover, as corrosion resistance can play an important role in practical applications, where a long in-service life has to be guaranteed, adapted surface treatments need to be considered. Protective coatings for metal surfaces include epoxy and chromium based coatings. These are efficient as adhesion promoters as well as corrosion inhibitors. However epoxy easily absorbs moisture, which may weaken the interfacial adhesion strength due to the diffusion of the absorbed water into the epoxy-metal interface, whereas chromium based coatings are generally highly toxic. Silane coupling agents offer the potential to overcome these problems [1]. Another advantage of using organofunctional silanes with steel is the potential inhibition of steel corrosion.

One of the most used and investigated silane is the aminofunctional silane with the general formula $H_2N-R-Si-(OR')_3$ [2, 3]. These silanes differ from general organosilanes in that they carry an aminofunctional group in the organic chain. This group is responsible for the specific chemical reaction behaviour and high reactivity of the basic aminosilane molecules. When applied onto a metallic surface, organofunctional silanes are supposed to bond to the metal surface via the formation of oxane bonds (MO-Si) induced by the interaction of silanol groups with the metal oxide surface as mentioned by Plueddemann [3] and DiBenedetto[4]. According to recent studies by Roche *et al.* [5, 6] on epoxy/metal systems, a partial dissolution of the metallic oxide layer by the basic aminosilane is expected. They have shown that the polymer/metal interphase consists of an organometallic complex resulting from both dissolution and diffusion phenomena which may partially precipitate to form needle-like crystals. In recent work, Bouchet *et al.* [7-9] have shown that these crystals formed in epoxy/metal interphases act as a corrosion inhibitor and considerably improve the Young's modulus of the resulting interphase formed between the oxide and the polymer.

In the case of applications where mechanical properties are an issue, a thorough understanding of the chemical and physical reactions, which take place in the silane/metal interphase is thus required to interpret the final overall properties of composite systems, such as corrosion resistance, adhesion and durability.

Silane coatings, however, are brittle compared to the steel substrate, in particular if they are applied as a thick coating. The coating may thus crack during further material forming or in use if high strains are expected. As a consequence, it is necessary to optimise adhesion together with the mechanical behaviour of the silane interphase.

Hyperbranched polymers (HBP) [10] are highly branched macromolecules in a three-dimensional globular architecture, with a large number of end groups. The chain end groups can be functionalised with tailored groups to ensure compatibility and reactivity with a surrounding matrix. Used as additives in epoxy resins, they give enhanced flexibility and/or increased toughening due to phase separation and without affecting other properties, such as hardness and tensile modulus [11-14]. HBP have also found use as compatibilizer at the interface of polypropylene and polyamide 6 [15]. A former study has shown that HBP may exert a toughening effect on thick hybrid HBP/silane coatings [16] inducing a potential benefit on the stress transfer between the metal substrate and the polymer.

This article thus presents a study of the practical adhesion between galvanised steel and polyethylene using a functionalised organo-silane as a coupling agent. Adhesion is characterised by three-point flexure tests [8]. Several alternatives are compared in order to select a possible surface treatment and optimise the interfacial adhesion performance. Hyperbranched polymers (HBP) are used to toughen the silane coating [11]. Maleic anhydride is also used to enhance the polarity of polyethylene and to introduce a reactive group for the organosilanes from the polymer side. The physico-chemical interaction between the hydrolysed or oxide layers of the metallic substrate and the amino based silane coating is analysed using various analytical techniques such as FTIR, optical microscopy, ICP and topographical studies of the steel surface (SEM).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The metallic substrates are 1.5mm thick commercial electrolytically zinc coated cold rolled flat steel, corresponding to the standard reference EN 10152 and purchased at Debrunner SA, Switzerland.

The polymer is a chemically modified polyethylene, called ELTEX ADB52 and supplied by BP-Solvay polyethylenes, Belgium. It is a maleic anhydride grafted polyethylene (MAH-g-PE).

The metallic substrates were coated with a liquid γ -(Aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (γ -APS), 99% pure from GE materials, Switzerland. The natural pH of the γ -APS as received is close to 12.

The modifier is an epoxy functional HBP, BoltornTM-E1, supplied by Perstorp, Sweden. This hyperbranched polymer has an epoxy equivalent weight of 1080 g/eq and a theoretical epoxy-functionality of 9.72.

Adhesion testing of galvanised steel – polyolefin coated systems

For practical adhesion measurement three-point flexure measurements were performed according to the international standard ISO 14679.

The metallic substrates were cut to provide identically sized strips of dimensions 10mm x 100mm. Before any polymer or coating application, the substrates were acetone cleaned by wiping with an acetone dipped paper, and subsequently cleaned ultrasonically in an acetone bath and wiped dry with a soft absorbent paper.

Two different types of coatings were applied to the galvanized steel substrates: pure γ -APS or hybrid HBP/ γ -APS coatings with different wt% of HBP. The different coatings were applied by immersing the substrates in additive/isopropanol solutions. Two different concentrations of γ -APS/isopropanol solutions (1wt% and 5wt%) were used to vary the thickness of the final coatings. The hybrid coatings were applied by dipping in 5wt% isopropanol solutions. The solutions were prepared either from fresh basic γ -APS/isopropanol solutions or a solution controlled at a neutral pH (using 1M of acetic acid), measured at pH8. A summary of all the coatings applied with the different conditions is given in table 1. After a dipping procedure of 10 min, the substrates were placed in a climatic chamber at 60°C and a controlled relative humidity of 50%R.H. during 24 hours for curing. The substrates are then kept in a dessicator with humidity absorbing silica gel until further use.

table 1: Summary of the different coatings applied to the galvanised steel substrates.

	Pure γ -APS coatings				Hybrid HBP/ γ -APS coatings									
HBP Boltorn E1 [wt%]					1	2	3	4	5					
γ -APS [wt%]	100				99	98	97	96	95					
Additive in isopropanol solution [wt%]	1		5		5									
pH of the solution (b- basic ; n-neutral)	b	n	b	n	b	n	b	n	b	n	b	n	b	n

For practical adhesion measurement, a block of MAH-g-PE was applied on each substrate. The polymer deposit was shaped within a silicon mould held against the substrate by a clamping system. The polymer block had dimensions of 25x5x8mm³. The mould was adapted to thermoplastic materials, with a piston shaped insert and a weight to apply compression during cooling of the part. The assembly was heated up to 150°C in 45min and cooled down to room temperature using a water cooling system integrated in the mould.

Ageing of the samples was carried out by immersing them in distilled water at 50°C during 12h.

The bonded specimens were submitted to a continuous strain at a constant speed using a three point flexure test set-up in a UTS tensile testing machine equipped with a 1kN load cell (see fig. 1). The crosshead displacement speed was 1 mm/min. The maximum force F_{max} at delamination was recorded.

fig. 1: View of the 3-point flexure test.

Observation of silane/oxide interactions

Before any coating application, the metal substrate surfaces were ultrasonically degreased in acetone for 20 min and wiped dry with a soft absorbent paper. Some substrate surfaces were coated with gold using a E5400 High Resolution Sputter Coater (Bio-RAD Division).

To investigate the chemical and physical changes that may appear in liquid oligomers, through specific interaction with the oxide, γ -APS (pH = 12 or 8) was applied on a galvanized steel substrate (100x100 mm²) to form a 100-150 μ m thick liquid layer and kept at room temperature for up to 60 min in a dessicator under a continuous nitrogen flow to prevent any oligomer carbonation or oxidation. The obtained liquid, referred to as galvanised steel modified γ -APS (pH = 12 or 8), was then recovered with a PTFE spatula and stored in polypropylene vials under a nitrogen atmosphere.

The chemical structure of oligomers was investigated using a Fourier transform infrared spectrometer (FTIR Magma-IR 560 from Nicolet) with Omnic FTIR software. The samples were analyzed in the transmission mode in the range of 400–4000 cm⁻¹ using a DTGS detector. For each spectrum, 64 scans were collected at 4 cm⁻¹ resolution.

FTIR imaging was performed on a cured hybrid coating, using a Spectrum Spotlight from Perkin Elmer. This method allows the detection of chemical species from a specific spatial region and illustrates the results as an image with maximum and minimum absorbance of the chemical specie.

In order to check for any metallic ion diffusion through the liquid silane after application onto a metallic surface, inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectroscopy was done on a Perkin Elmer Plasma 200. The metallic substrates were galvanized steel as explained above and 1mm thick Zinc foils (99.95% purity) from Goodfellow, Great Britain. Deionized water was used as the solvent for the measurement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pure γ -APS coatings

The adherence properties of the MAH-g-PE / galvanised steel bonded joints were evaluated with a 3-point flexure configuration at room temperature, as explained above. A typical load-displacement curve is given in fig. 2. The maximum force detected at delamination was recorded for each sample tested. Although the maximum force is not well adapted for samples debonding in the plastic range of the substrate, it is used in the present study to provide a preliminary comparable indication of the bond performance. In the future, a detailed study using the values of displacement at debonding will be performed.

Average values for 6 samples tested with the different treatments are given in fig. 3. The initial average value measured at failure for the non treated galvanised steel samples, was 282N, whereas all the MAH-g-PE ribs completely delaminated in the ageing bath.

The use of silane increases the practical adhesion of MAH-g-PE towards galvanised steel, independently of the pH of the silane solution in the coating process. The effect of silane is clearly observed after ageing. All the coated samples, except those with 5% APS at pH8, still retain an adhesion performance equal to 63% of the initial value for the 1%APS coating and to 58% of the initial value for the 5%APS coating at pH12. The influence of the pH is well observed in the case of a thicker γ -APS layer: at neutral pH, the practical adhesion almost drops to zero, whereas at the basic pH of the silane, the residual adherence of the bond is about 58% of the initial value. The larger value of the standard deviation in the case of 1% γ -APS applied at pH 8 also indicates the lower performance of the bonded joint with ageing.

fig. 2: Typical load-displacement curve of a three-point flexure test. (a):substrate alone. (b) bonded sample.

fig. 3: Adherence of bonded samples with different γ -APS treatments.

It has been observed that for the non-treated samples, all the MAH-g-PE ribs without exception delaminated completely in the ageing bath, whereas for the samples with a coating of 5%APS at pH8, some of the ribs still adhered on the galvanised steel substrates. The sample test configuration could however not permit to measure a debonding force with partially delaminated samples. The concentration of the γ -APS in the coating solutions, i.e the thickness of the final coating, also exerts an influence on the practical adhesion of the bonded joints, although the effect is not systematic.

In general, it can be concluded that thick coatings at basic pH perform best, in contrary to literature, where it is mostly reported that a lower pH is preferred. However, a former study [16] has shown that a partial dissolution of the metal substrate in contact with the basic γ -APS leads to the presence of crystals at the interface, potentially responsible for the ageing performance of the samples with a thick γ -APS coating applied at pH12.

To characterize this effect, basic and neutral γ -APS in the liquid state were placed in contact with the galvanized substrates. In contrast to the initially transparent γ -APS, galvanized steel modified γ -APS (pH=basic) became milky white following contact with the metal oxide surfaces for 45 min. The recovered liquid, placed into test tubes, underwent a separation and the liquid part remained transparent, whereas the precipitate was milky white, as observed on fig. 4. A similar result was previously reported with basic isophorone diamine (IPDA), applied onto either titanium or aluminum substrates [6, 9]. Using the γ -APS controlled at pH 8 no colour change was observed.

fig. 4: Separation into a transparent liquid part and a milky white precipitation of the recovered liquid after contact with galvanised steel substrates.

Transmittance FTIR spectra of pure γ -APS, and γ -APS applied onto a gold coated substrate were identical, which indicates that no reaction occurred between γ -APS and gold. In contrast, FTIR spectra of galvanised steel modified γ -APS exhibited new bands suggesting that the γ -APS reacts with the oxide or hydrated surfaces. For the liquid γ -APS controlled at pH 8, transmittance FTIR spectra of galvanised steel modified γ -APS were identical to the spectra of pure γ -APS suggesting that there is no modification of the chemical structure of the γ -APS solution controlled at pH 8 when it is applied to oxide or hydroxide surfaces. Similar results were previously reported with the same γ -APS on glass and steel surfaces [16].

fig. 5: Crystal formation in the silane when applied to galvanised steel substrates.

fig. 6: Detailed view of a single needle.

The precipitate of the recovered steel modified γ -APS (fig. 4) was placed between two glass plates and observed under an optical microscope. Needles, such as shown in fig. 5 (with a detailed view of a single needle in fig. 6) were observed in the modified γ -APS liquid. According to the former FTIR observations, these needles are supposed to result from the precipitation of the newly formed species responsible for the milky white aspect of the precipitate. No particles were observed in galvanised steel modified γ -APS at pH 8. These observations were confirmed by ICP spectroscopy done on the precipitated part (see fig. 4) of the recovered liquid applied on galvanised steel and pure Zn substrates and referred to as galvanised steel modified γ -APS and pure Zn modified γ -APS respectively. The three samples were at pH12 and were diluted in distilled water by down to 2vol% for measurement. The concentration of Zn ions was determined and is given in fig. 7. Compared to the initial γ -APS, both modified γ -APS samples clearly show an increase of the Zn ion concentration.

fig. 7: ICP analysis of pure γ -APS, galvanised steel and pure Zn modified γ -APS at natural pH. The content of Zn ions are given for 0.2vol% distilled water solutions.

These observations of crystal formation, only in the case of basic γ -APS, confirm that the hydrated metallic oxide is dissolved by the amino-silane, and that complexes precipitate after the solubility limit is overcome. Since the cure of the non pre-hydrolysed amino-silane is slow at 60°C, it is thought that this happens as well in the thin coating during cure, and leads to enhanced properties of the coating deposited at the natural pH.

Hybrid HBP/ γ APS coatings

(a) coating applied at pH8

(a) coating applied at pH12

fig. 8: Adherence of bonded samples with different hybrid HBP/ γ -APS coatings.

fig. 9: Influence of ageing on practical adhesion.

For adhesion performance, measured by three-point flexure tests, no positive influence of the HBP was observed, regardless of the pH, as shown in fig. 8. Indeed, the more HBP is added, the more the adherence of the joints drops. With ageing, at pH 8, the samples delaminated during ageing whereas at pH 12 a residual adhesion of all the bonds is observed. Moreover it seems that the adherence loss after ageing is reduced as the amount of HBP is increased, as shown in fig. 8 (b). A linear relationship can even be stated between the HBP content and the relative drop of F_{max} . This rule is however not followed by the 5wt% HBP/ γ -APS coating. In agreement with the observation concerning the pure silane coating, the coating applied at pH 12 performs better than that applied at pH 8.

In order to enhance the phenomena occurring at the oxide/coating interface, a detailed study was carried out on oxide modified γ -APS mixed with HBP. When curing is performed in-situ

within a hot stage under an optical microscope, the crystals do not dissolve during the curing cycle (60°C, 12h), as shown in fig. 10.

fig. 10: In-situ observation of the curing of a hybrid γ -APS/HBP mixture.

FTIR imaging performed on these cured samples (fig. 11) reveals that a phase separation occurs inducing the formation of a new epoxy network with the unprecipitated crystals. Indeed, maximum absorbance of both epoxy and amine are detected in the same regions, precisely in the regions of the highest concentrations of the crystals.

fig. 11: Imaging by FTIR spectroscopy of a hybrid hybrid γ -APS/HBP coating onto a metallic substrate.

fig. 12: New network formation when mixing HBP to steel modified γ -APS and applied and cured on a metallic surface.

As a new network (see fig. 12) is formed when adding HBP to γ -APS, it is highly possible that the curing kinetics of the coating are affected, most probably reduced by the phase separation. This could explain the reduction in adherence of the hybrid coatings, compared to the pure γ -APS coatings. One possible explanation of the increase of the adhesion

performance of the hybrid coatings with ageing could then be a “postcuring” of the coatings in presence of water in the ageing bath.

CONCLUSIONS

Silane coatings were investigated as coupling agents between MAH-g-PE and galvanised steel substrates, in terms of adhesion performance, and residual adhesion after aging in water. It was observed that both the thickness of the coating and the pH at which they are applied influence the adhesion performance of the bonded samples. Durability studies mainly show that coatings applied at basic pH perform best. This can be related to the observed partial dissolution of metal surface ions into the coating resulting in the formation of sharp needle like crystals when the solubility limit is overcome.

Epoxidized hyperbranched polymer (HBP) were also used as reaction modifiers with amino-silane, to take advantage of their potential toughening role. An interaction with uncrystallized organo-metallic complexes was observed, with the resulting formation of a new network. Due to possible uncomplete curing of the coatings, initial adhesion of these hybrid coatings is reduced. Ageing of the bonded samples lead to a less drastic loss of adhesion than in the case of the pure silane coatings. The hybrid coatings seem to provide an interesting route but as the phenomena occurring at the interface during cure are not yet well identified, further studies are needed to enhance the performance of these hybrid coatings.

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